

SOCIAL AND POLICY INTERVENTIONS MANUAL

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Credits

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Background

Introduction

This Manual on social and policy interventions aims to offer EU countries targeted guidelines and insights on health and social care as well as policy and social measures. It shows which measures are suitable for prevention and containment of transmittable diseases in different contexts and pandemic phases and to what extent communication is decisive for their successful implementation.

The current COVID-19 pandemic has had a strong impact on everyday life and has created an unprecedented challenge to health and care systems worldwide. Numerous measures to respond to the urgent care needs of those impacted have been taken, while also trying to reduce the long-term impact on vulnerable people in all possible ways. Since the first cases appeared, countries have developed several strategies, adapted services, and introduced a wide range of innovations, all requiring flexibility, especially to address people's continued care. Since the emergency state period, a collaborative leadership approach has turned out to be essential, and working together in partnership, investing in participatory citizenship, is key.

The emergency state, the use of teleworking, social distancing and all the new methods and measures that have been implemented have helped to understand society's greatest fragilities and have entailed changes in work, education, tools and routines with potential long-term impacts. Younger and more digital generations have found it easier to adapt to living 'remotely' during restrictions. Adults with lower qualifications and skills need to be supported with targeted information, especially on health. They also need social type of data, as they are easily hampered in the search for reliable information due to the lack of digital skills.

Apart from all the innovations and ideas that are being and have been developed and new ways of delivering services, there is the need to prepare bottom-up initiatives that enhance the competences of care professionals, so that they are prepared to cope with such emergency situations in the future.

These are, among others, the goals of the STEP_UP project, that will be achieved through an educational online game as well as a workshop and training framework containing a lot of useful and reliable knowledge.

The STEP_UP Project

The STEP_UP project is coordinated by SHINE 2 Europe, based in Portugal. The other partners are: the Croatian Institute of Public Health (CIPH), WISE Angle from Spain, the Institute for Social Infrastructure (ISIS) from Germany and AFEdeMy from the Netherlands.

STEP_UP means 'Stop Epidemic Growth Through Learning'. The overall goal of the project is to create an interactive educational game that helps to identify possible responses to a pandemic outbreak and assess their impact on society and the spread of transmittable diseases. The game has been developed for adult learners such as **care professionals, community leaders, informal caregivers** and **volunteers**, but can also be enjoyed by society as a whole. Players are introduced to the actual impact of behaviours during the spread of a pandemic and the arrival of emergency situations. They can thus learn about communication, social prevention, care and political measures, and their impacts on different levels. (See the **Project Outcomes** section to learn more about the game).

As there is already plenty of information about pandemics and epidemics that is available online, it is difficult to know what information is reliable. Therefore, preparing the right training methods to approach adult learners in a suitable and engaging way is a must. To achieve this, a learning framework is being developed to stimulate interactive education within the target group.

To further support confidence-inspiring sources of information and report on measures against transmittable diseases that are used in practice, a digital database has also been created within the STEP_UP project (more information under the **Project Outcomes** section). This database lists more than 200 measures that have been implemented in practice. The database can also be consulted by country or area using several filters and is available in English and the partnership languages.

As a project outcome, this Manual aims to provide easily understandable and reliable information on how to deal with pandemic situations. Based on interventions taken from practice, it offers targeted guidelines and insights on communication, social, health care and policy measures for EU countries. The aim is also to explain that there are different pandemic phases during which the measures can have a different impact. The Manual provides easily accessible and useful information to advisors with practical examples, lessons that have been learned and successful outcomes for the different stages of health emergencies during disease outbreaks.

Approach

This Manual is the result of active research within a comprehensive structure and design.

In order to draft the Manual, each partner in the STEP_UP project prepared a thematic report on possible responses to COVID-19 and other communicable diseases in a specific area. The reports covered possible measures to counteract communicable diseases and were divided as follows:

- **WISE** from Spain compiled communication measures.
- **SHINE** from Portugal dealt with a wide range of social prevention measures.
- **ISIS** from Germany summarised policy measures.
- **CIPH** from Croatia gathered health and social care measures.
- **AFEdemy** from the Netherlands dealt with measures for the early detection of communicable diseases.

Based on the thematic reports, a quantitative expert survey was conducted during which the STEP_UP target groups were asked to evaluate the measures that had been compiled. A total of 133 people were surveyed in all the partner countries and others too. Respondents were mainly public health and social care workers, healthcare professionals, volunteers and municipality officials, but also lecturers, researchers, or people from the business sector. The aim of the survey was four-fold: a) evaluate the recommendations that had been directly made by users; b) present practical suggestions for improvement; c) maximise the content of knowledge; and d) outline the possible impact of the measures. As well as the thematic reports and the survey, an online library was created with over 200 pandemic-related measures and practices adopted by partner countries and worldwide.

The Manual, as the last step in the research cycle, combines the information from the thematic reports with more recent findings, the recommendations of the target groups from the STEP_UP survey and practical examples of measures from the virtual library.

In the manual, after being introduced to different communicable diseases, you will be given an overview of different phases that are common to pandemic situations. The measures that are described in the manual cover four different areas: after investigating how to increase confidence in necessary interventions or how to prevent misinformation in **Communication Measures**, you will learn about efforts that can be made by everyone in society in the area of **Social Measures** and **Care Measures** that promote specific organisational processes and interventions in health care. The last section contains **Political Measures** which include the establishment of task forces, restrictions for businesses and public services, or vaccination measures.

More information on all the other project outputs (Thematic reports, STEP_UP survey, virtual library and the educational game to be released in February 2023) can be found under the **Project Outcomes** section.

Epidemics and Pandemics as Recurring Events

Communicable diseases have plagued mankind since time immemorial. In many cases, science has been able to find solutions to keep the spread and burden of these diseases under control. Sometimes, however, a new disease breaks out and the number of cases increases unexpectedly (epidemic) or undergoes exponential growth thus affecting several countries and populations (pandemic) before effective solutions are found. The most recent example of such a pandemic is COVID-19.

It is not possible to think that no other health emergency situations will occur in the future. To enable the target group of adult learners of STEP_UP to be prepared for future outbreaks, it is also important to focus on measures taken when epidemics or pandemics infested Europe in the past or are compatible with COVID-19.

Black Death/Plague (Epidemic)

The Black Death or Plague is a bubonic plague that struck Europe and Asia in many different centuries. The plague caused many casualties: according to estimates, about 50% of the populations were killed. The plague is spread by a bacillus that passes from person to person through airborne particles, or through bites from infected fleas and rats. Symptoms are black boils oozing blood and pus covering the body. The disease was incredibly powerful: people could go to bed healthy and be dead in the morning. Prevention from the plague entails making the environment rodent-proof, avoiding skin contact and controlling fleas on pets. Plague vaccines are in development but are not expected to be commercially available in the immediate future.

1918 H1N1 / Spanish Flu (Pandemic)

The 1918 H1N1 flu pandemic, sometimes referred to as the 'Spanish flu', killed an estimated 50 million people worldwide. Mortality was high among children below 5 years of age, people between 20 and 40 years of age and people over 65. An unusual characteristic of this virus was the high mortality it caused among healthy adults aged 15 to 34. At that time there was no vaccine to protect against influenza and no antibiotics to treat secondary bacterial infections. Control efforts were limited to interventions such as isolation, quarantine, good personal hygiene, use of disinfectants, and limitations of public gatherings.

SARS-CoV (Pandemic)

Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) is a viral respiratory illness caused by a coronavirus called SARS-associated coronavirus (SARS-CoV). SARS was first reported in Asia in February 2003. The illness spread to more than two dozen countries in North America, South America, Europe, and Asia before the SARS global outbreak of 2003 was contained. Since 2004, there have not been any known cases of SARS anywhere in the world. In general, SARS begins with a high fever (temperature > 38 degrees Celsius). Other symptoms may include headache, general discomfort and body aches. Some people also have mild respiratory symptoms at the outset. Most patients develop pneumonia. SARS is spread by close person-to-person contact and airborne droplets.

2009 H1N1 / Mexican Flu (Pandemic)

In 2009 an influenza (flu) virus emerged that had never been seen before in humans. This virus contained a unique combination of influenza genes that had not been previously identified in animals or people. The United States Center for Disease Control and Prevention estimated that 150,000-575,000 people worldwide died during the first year the virus circulated. According to estimates, 80% of these deaths occurred in people under 65 years of age. This is quite different from typical seasonal influenza epidemics, during which about 70-90% of deaths are estimated to involve people older than 65. Nowadays an effective vaccine is available and many younger people were vaccinated in 2010.

MERS (Pandemic)

Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) broke out in 2012 and is an illness caused by a virus (more specifically, a coronavirus) called Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV). Most MERS patients develop severe respiratory illnesses with symptoms of fever, cough and shortness of breath. About 3 or 4 out of every 10 patients with MERS have died. MERS-CoV can be spread through close contact, such as caring for or living with an infected person. Preventive measures are: washing hands, covering mouth and nose with a tissue, avoiding personal contact and cleaning and disinfecting surfaces frequently.

SARS-CoV-2 Coronavirus (Pandemic)

On 31 December, the Chinese government reported the first official cases of this coronavirus to the WHO.¹ Just one week later, the pathogen SARS-CoV-2 (Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus type 2) was identified in Wuhan, the outbreak site of the virus. Symptoms of the disease include: cough, fever, rhinitis, and disturbance of the sense of smell and taste. A particular international difficulty in dealing with this coronavirus has been its strong adaptability thanks to its polymorphic nucleotide positions. Ever new virus variants, such as the alpha, beta and omicron mutations, and a usually increasing transmissibility were also the reason why some countries had, or still have, to struggle with the coronavirus for a long time.² Worldwide, more than half a billion people have been identified with the coronavirus,³ with more than 6 million deaths (more than one million in the USA alone).⁴ COVID-19 is thus the most recent pandemic situation and has been a major organisational challenge due to its rapid transmission, which caused some countries to simply be overwhelmed by it.

The Corona pandemic has been particularly stressful for employees in the health sector. The development and implementation of new nursing concepts in combination with a pre-existing staff shortage and a considerable increase in the number of patients has led to incredible psychological strain for healthcare workers. This is also related to the fact that nursing workers were exposed to one of the greatest risks during the pandemic, which was due, among other things, to the fact that they were always in direct contact with infected persons.⁵

Pandemic Phases

Now that various past viral diseases have been described, it is important to better classify the various pandemic phases and to better understand the circumstances they create. After describing the early detection phase, the early outbreak will be described, followed by the epidemic or pandemic period and the re-opening and normalisation stage. Some measures that can be adopted during each of the phases will be presented. However, it is also important to understand that some measures are not limited to one specific period but can be used in more than one phase.

Early detection

The first pandemic phase entails early detection of the virus. Here, everybody's goal must be to learn from past pandemic situations such as SARS, Ebola and COVID-19. For example, when the first patient was infected in Wuhan, China, no one expected such a rapid spread, and lack of preparedness became apparent. Regarding social and policy interventions, the following questions should be asked: What can public authorities, healthcare providers and volunteers do to best assess outbreaks with the help of experts? How can we communicate with professionals and the general public, and which preparation measures are suitable and feasible before a disease even occurs?

One future solution could be to enable early detection of upcoming health emergencies and prevent the emergency from turning into a pandemic or epidemic. Early detection plays a crucial role in all treatment and prevention strategies and underlie a fixed order:

After exposure to a health threat, an incubation period follows. During that period a person can be infected but be unaware of the illness or be asymptomatic. In this latter case, the person can unknowingly infect others. Following the onset of symptoms, a variety of health behaviours and health encounters may occur depending on the severity of the symptoms. Examples are: searching for information on the internet, consulting an e-doctor or, if symptoms are more serious, visiting one's GP or local emergency unit. There, an initial diagnosis will be made, and samples may be sent off to laboratories for a definitive diagnosis. The time delay between exposure and confirmed diagnosis may be days, weeks or months depending on the type of infection.

Rapid and accurate identification of the underlying agent (the bacterium or virus) using diagnostic testing is essential to select the correct control measure, such as containment, confinement, antimicrobials, and vaccines. This is particularly true for emerging diseases, such as COVID-19, where society finds itself in a race to develop new controls as the disease spreads. In an outbreak situation, vigilant monitoring is vital to inform where to focus efforts and assess the effectiveness of interventions.

However, worldwide, many infections remain undetected. Due to poor diagnostic tools, infections are often undiagnosed and therefore untreated, or diagnosed at the late stage when treatment becomes less effective. This results in on-going transmission of serious infections, and delay in the identification of emerging threats leading to major human and economic negative consequences for millions of people.⁶

Early outbreak

The early outbreak phase of a virus usually begins with the clear identification of the first infected person with a new disease (patient zero). Key questions in the early outbreak phase are how to ensure the safe handling of caregivers and volunteers, and what technological tracking methods are available. Furthermore, in this early phase, the question arises as to how the pandemic can be contained and how far-reaching should measures be.

Contact tracing, which can also be carried out socially via **Tracing Apps**, is essential in this pandemic phase. This should usually be linked to selected **Preventive measures** in the early stages. In addition, communication measures such as **Anti-disinformation measures** or to **Nurture trust in public health communication** are crucial to dispel possible false myths and give society confidence in the measures being introduced.

Epidemic disease or pandemic stage

The epidemic or pandemic stage of a communicable disease is reached as soon as large-scale spread occurs in the whole of society. Central questions in this phase are how to deal with the large number of patients and how to support the nursing staff accordingly. In addition, political questions must be asked as to how hospitalisation rates can be curbed with measures such as closures, and what social and communication interventions must be taken to protect society and increase its perception of danger.

Particularly crucial during this pandemic phase are organisational measures in the healthcare sector. For example, to **Increase staff and conduct trainings for employees performing unfamiliar tasks** can help to ensure that more efficient work is done even with existing personnel. At political level, it is also a matter of supporting the health sector through important **Financial resources / subsidies** to afford materials like test kits and protective devices or raise salaries and pay bonuses to health staff. A comprehensive **Lockdown** can be used to prevent transmission through contact. In the social context of personal responsibility and solidarity, **Quarantine / Self-isolation** can reduce the reproduction of a disease.

Exit strategy and opening-up

The final pandemic phase occurs when a sustained decline in the number of infections is observed over a longer period of time. However, the question in this situation is how to get back to normality.

Countries such as **China**, for example, have used a technological solution and developed a colour-based mobile phone application to tell its people their current status and rights. In the case of an infection, for instance, a red light shows up to prescribe 14 days of isolation. Thanks to this targeted technological solution, the unaffected part of the population should be able to live normally, while the infected part is allowed to test itself again after quarantine.

The **Spanish** government has tried a different approach since the end of March 2022. In their exit strategy, they are striving for the so-called 'fluisation' of the virus, i.e., the gradual treatment of COVID-19 as a normal flu. This is intended to gradually bring conditions back to normal.⁷

A different policy was adopted by the **Netherlands**, which lifted all its preventive measures against Corona in March 2022 and only continued with the observation of the virus.⁸

Vaccination

The exit strategy and the opening-up phase is also strongly dependent on successful societal **Vaccination measures**. These should be taken when vaccines that have been proven safe are ready for use. In order to implement a vaccination campaign successfully, it is also essential to **Nurture trust in public health communication** to convince the society. Together with an adjusted use of **Preventive measures** and vaccination, increased risk perception and trust in healthcare through communication can be a key intervention in preventing the ongoing spread of transmittable diseases. This approach is needed to make a huge impact on putting an end to an epidemic or a pandemic.

Measures

In this second part of the Manual, specific measures are described, and background information on the areas where they can be implemented is given. An overview of the different areas and the specific measures can be found below:

Communication Measures

- Nurture trust in public health communication
- Incorporate societal values, emotions, and stories
- Anti-disinformation measures
- Institutionalise communication and tailor strategies for different target groups
- Foster public engagement

Social Measures

- Preventive measures
- Tracing Apps
- Testing measures
- Quarantine / Self-isolation

Care Measures

- Contact tracing
- Establish an isolation ward
- Increase staff and conduct trainings for employees performing unfamiliar tasks

Political Measures

- Building a taskforce
- Financial resources / subsidies
- Lockdown
- Restrictions of businesses / schools / public services / mass gatherings
- Vaccination measures

Every measure in these areas will be described below. They will also be accompanied by an impact assessment, potential suggestions for improvement gained in the STEP_UP survey, and practical examples of how each measure has been applied. In the introduction to the different areas of application, you will find useful guidelines and background knowledge on the field. In addition, you will find some links to events from the STEP_UP educational game. More information is available in the **Project Outcomes** section. Links to events are given to support learning about practical implementation and a gamified experience.

COMMUNICATION MEASURES

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Communication Measures

There is no communication ‘best practice’ during a complex public health emergency. However, experience has led to establish several principles that may contribute to a successful strategy.

Several guides published by the World Health Organization (WHO), the US Centers for Disease Prevention and Control (CDC), and other organisations outline good communication based on lessons learned from past health crises, including Ebola and Zika.⁹

Despite the abundance of guidance documents, it is important to highlight the main factor that makes COVID-19 different from previous medical crises, partly because of universal access to communication technologies. “This is the first pandemic of its kind in the age of social media,” explains K. Vish Viswanath, Lee Kum Kee Professor of Health Communication and director of the Applied Risk Communication for the 21st Century programme at the Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. “Because of the saturated information environment, we are getting overwhelmed, even though each medium is covering information in a careful and responsible way, especially the mainstream press” he explains. “The collective exposure is causing stress. People are struggling with how to stem the tide of information flooding them.”¹⁰

It is also relevant to stress that most reports and publications focus on risk communication strategies. Studies have suggested that risk communication strategies are an effective non-pharmaceutical intervention (NPI) for COVID-19;¹¹ other NPIs could include travel restrictions, physical distancing, or personal protective equipment — each of which, in turn, requires clear communications. Moreover, accurate communication about the fast-track adoption of political measure and the use of emergency funds is crucial to enhance transparency and accountability in government decisions. Finally, the role of communication and government efforts to build trust in vaccines has undoubtedly become evident, as highlighted by the OECD which has also collected a series of good practices and lessons learnt.¹²

Several studies have centred their analysis on identifying lessons from social psychology and cognitive science that inform how to communicate with clarity and motivational power to encourage behavioural shifts. In spite of this, the extent to which behavioural insights are able to change behaviour within the context of COVID-19 are still not completely understood.¹³

In general, we have witnessed that risk communication has been increasingly handled, planned, and delivered in conjunction with community engagement actions thus moving from the directive, one-way communication, which characterised the early stages of the COVID-19 response, towards the community engagement and participatory approaches that have proven to help control and eliminate outbreaks in the past.¹⁴

The field of communication measures is the first of the four different categories of interventions in this Manual. This is because balanced communication about the measures that follow in the other chapters is essential for their use and society's general risk awareness during a pandemic. After the key challenges are presented, the recommendations that follow are intended to help improve communication and understanding in future pandemic situations.

By whom and where can communication measures be introduced?

Communication measures can be adopted at almost all levels: everyone has the right to express their opinion. However, various institutions and organisations such as sports clubs or state facilities and bodies can also communicate through announcements. The communication measures listed in this section can be applied both individually and institutionally in informal and governmental environments.

Key Challenges to Effective Communication

Many contextual and behavioural factors influence the impact of communication during health crises.

Communication shall adjust to changing information needs

- Leão et al. report data from a content analysis of 293 questions submitted to online, radio, newspaper and TV channel forums during the first months of the pandemic in Portugal. They found a high degree of uncertainty and doubt about medical issues, infection control, daily life practicalities concerning the lockdown and other related measures.¹⁵
- “Every crisis has a life cycle, and emotional states and needs vary with the cycle’s stages”. Starting from this assumption, the leaders’ guide released by McKinsey (2020) frames a crisis in three evolving steps which communicators should be aware of: (a) In the crisis’s early stages, governments and major media outlets first focused on clear, simple instructions about physical distancing and ‘lockdown’ guidelines; (b) as people began to follow safety instructions, communication shifted and focussed on adjusting to change and uncertainty, e.g., from health basics to socio-economic recovery; (c) finally, as the crisis’s end comes into view (which is still too early on a broader perspective), communication shall strive to help people make sense of its magnitude and impact.¹⁶

People do not generally understand the scientific process

- Scientific research progressed as long as measures were being implemented. For instance, guidelines on masking, vaccines for individual age groups and safe and unsafe behaviour evolved.
- In an era dominated by social media, and a general problem with people mistrusting public authorities, this could convey to the public the wrong feeling that “science was changing its mind and coming up with contradictory recommendations, flip-flopping on issues”. However, “That’s how science is done. It’s always about changing your position based on new information”.¹⁷

Information processing is affected by stress and uncertainty

- In general, people may not hear, remember, or misinterpret information.
- People hold on to tightly held beliefs and may be less likely to engage in behaviour that they perceive to be counterintuitive.
- People may exhibit ‘confirmation bias’ i.e., the tendency to favour, search for, interpret and remember information that confirms our own beliefs. According to some experts, this might be one of the justifications behind the messages of calm issued by Spanish authorities in March 2020 despite the alarming information coming from other countries such as China, South Korea and Italy.¹⁸
- How messages are interpreted is also influenced by people’s tendency to exhibit ‘optimism bias’, i.e., overestimating the likelihood of positive events in our future while underestimating the likelihood of negative events. Such human cognition pattern has shown to reduce adherence to behavioural change.¹⁹

Emotions and social ties affect risk perception and decision making

- Emotions such as fear form the basis for judgements of risk. However, messages that incite fear tend to be successful only in producing a desired behaviour when people feel a strong sense of efficacy.²⁰
- Under stress, people tend towards herd behaviour, making decisions based on the behaviour of others. A study showed how individuals reacted to other people's panic buying following the global outbreak of COVID-19: not only were their feelings of anxiety triggered but they also tended to emulate them.²¹
- Perceived social norms among peers (e.g., family, friends, community) influence a person's likelihood to engage in a particular behaviour. Social networks can promote the spread of beneficial as well as harmful behaviour.
- Cultural norms and cultural identity factor strongly into how people make decisions but may also underlie disease risk. Messages need to be framed in a way that is culturally relevant to the target audience.²²

Stigma and misinformation lead to the rise of harmful stereotypes

- The United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF), the World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) define social stigma in the context of health as "the negative association between a person or group of people who share certain characteristics and a specific disease". The many unknown aspects of diseases and the fears associated to them have been fuelling stereotypes.²³
- In turn, people who are afraid of being stigmatised can be driven away from getting screened, diagnosed, and quarantined.
- The responsibility for nurturing and amplifying stigmas is collectively shared among policy makers, citizens and, most importantly, journalists. Some media outlets have, for example, focused on speculating on the source of COVID-19, trying to identify 'patient zero' in every county.

Suggested events including communication measures in the STEP_UP educational game

Event 7

Help **Katharina Fisher** to compile useful information on an info sheet and use trustful communication.

Incorporate social values and emotions

Foster public engagement

Event 15

Help **Dr. Francis Nelson** to dismantle false information and support him using trustworthy communication.

Nurture trust in public health

Anti-disinformation measures

Event 23

Help **Health Minister Britta Johnson** to communicate about the vaccination campaign and provide society with reliable information.

Institutionalise communication

[CLICK HERE TO ACCESS THE STEP_UP GAME](#)

Communication Measures

Nurture trust in public health communication

Description and possible impact

Trust is the key principle in communicating with others. This applies, for example, to risk and public health communication. Experts converge on defining trust as a 'vital driver' for behaviour shifts and acceptance of measures. Reasons for mistrust are varied and relate to structural, historical, and cultural factors that can also lead to disinformation (See [Anti-disinformation measures](#)). Understanding them is key to developing trust-building strategies.

Without trust, people will not believe in or act on the information provided by health officials or experts.²⁴ Recent global data suggest that people tend to have the highest levels of trust in information shared by scientists, doctors, and health experts (68%), followed by WHO (56%).²⁵

However, trusted and credible institutions not only have to focus on risk communication and messages aimed to support the application of public health measures: during a crisis, timely and accurate updates on the utilisation of emergency relief funds are fundamental to enhance transparency and public accountability.²⁶

Moreover, this was a crisis that heightened and revamped prior political arguments around personal autonomy and individual rights and freedoms. It has sparked an interesting debate on the extent to which health communications can also be democratic if they encourage forms of democratic practice.²⁷ Because of this, it is also regarded as important for communicators to convey respect and a belief that they trust the public, as this is more likely to elicit cooperation autonomously.²⁸

Healthcare professionals and workers surveyed in the STEP_UP project named higher acceptance of the measures as a positive result of trustworthy communication. On the other hand, they stated that in future pandemics initial uncertainties about the diseases must be communicated from day one, as this honesty also strengthens trust. They also suggested offering communication training as a possible solution to better prepare hospital staff to provide trustworthy information.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Acknowledge uncertainty; explain what is known/unknown.
- Be honest and recognise if you do not have an answer.
- Be transparent, explain what actions are being taken and why.
- Disclose what evidence was used to inform public-health recommendations, who was consulted, and what scenarios and trade-offs were considered.
- Employ mechanisms of accountability, such as releasing digestible information on COVID-19 expenditures and their impact.
- Rely on messengers who are competent and experts in the field.
- Be consistent when releasing messages.
- Use simple messages.
- Correct misinformation (see [Anti-disinformation measures](#)).

Don'ts

- Over-reassure.
- Foster unrealistic expectations.
- Draw too much attention to misinformation.

Nurturing trust through experts

Germany: Former Chancellor Angela Merkel used science and clear explanations of the epidemiological basis for her government's lockdown exit strategy.²⁹ Likewise, Christian Dorsten, a leading coronavirus virologist in Germany and advisor to Angela Merkel, launched a podcast in February to explain the science behind the virus as well as the latest research on it.

Spain: During the peak of the crisis, the Spanish government soon opted for delegating health and science messages to the Head of the Health Ministry's Coordination Centre for Health Alerts, Dr. Fernando Simón. Through daily reports on Spanish national television channels, Simón quickly became the voice of science. His broadcasts at around 18.00pm from Monday to Friday became a daily feature for Spanish citizens to find out about the latest developments in the national epidemiological situation.³⁰

Portugal: In order to build trust in the national vaccination campaign, the Portuguese Directorate General of Health recruited 5000 micro-influencers who were able to provide trusted information to communities. Thanks to this personal and social approach, this decision helped to dispel doubts early on in the crisis and has also contributed to Portugal having one of the highest vaccination rates in Europe today.³¹

Communication Measures

Incorporate societal values, emotions, and stories

Description and possible impacts

Every society has a social contract that frames the way we act and prioritise decisions and choices. One of the key lessons for a global response to a pandemic is that the cultural logic of different societies shapes and influences their prevention strategies.³²

A recent study in the US confirmed the need for promoting pro-social values: compared to messages that induce fear, pro-social messages capable of arousing a positive emotional state have proved to be more effective in accepting measures such as self-isolation.³³ Moreover, high level of civic awareness and voluntary cooperation have demonstrated that they can strengthen collective efforts to overcome this public health emergency, as was the case in South Korea.

Volunteers and social care workers interviewed as part of the STEP_UP project stated that the positive results of promoting pro-social values included strengthening the social sense of solidarity and the role of personal responsibility in the pandemic. On the other hand, interviewees stated that the promotion of these values had not reached some parts of the population and that it would be necessary to open the debate without focussing too much on values to make the measure even more effective.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Focus on messages of solidarity, kindness, and love.
- Appeal to the 'common' good.
- Link behaviours to people's identities.
- Focus on people adopting desirable behaviour.
- Outline stories encouraging public cooperation.
- Mobilise people who have recovered from COVID-19 to act as community champions to build social trust and hope.
- Respect cultural beliefs/values.

Don'ts

- Don't draw attention to undesirable behaviour.
- Do not scare but provide sufficient information for recipients to be 'appropriately worried'.
- Do not use militaristic analogies/metaphors that may increase stress and fear.
- Don't use wording or narratives that may encourage discrimination or segregation.

Anti-disinformation measures in practice

New Zealand: Jacinda Ardern streamed her conversations with regular New Zealanders to share their stories and advice in "Conversations through COVID".³⁴ On 25 March, as the country's national lockdown began, Ardern recorded a message from her couch at home to express sympathy.³⁵

Italy: Prime Minister Giuseppe Conte has been quoted as the builder of memorable sentences in his speeches pushing towards national sacrifice, good will and common values. A notable example was the concept of "staying apart today so that we can go back to hugging tomorrow".³⁶

Communication Measures

Anti-disinformation measures

Description and possible impact

Pandemic-related misinformation and disinformation started shortly after the outbreak of the coronavirus. According to European Commission Vice-President Vera Jourava: "The COVID-19 pandemic has been accompanied by an unprecedented 'infodemic'". False claims included statements according to which the virus was spread as a pretext for forced mass vaccination; another one allegedly reported that the pandemic is a way for Microsoft founder Bill Gates, working together with the EU, to monitor people.³⁷ Anti-disinformation measures are meant to counter such conspiracy theories.

Disinformation strategies can be found in all pandemics. Target groups of countermeasures are conspiracy theorists, members of online platforms, people with certain health conditions and the general public who needs to be informed about incorrect information.

Anti-disinformation measures counter false claims and equip individuals with arguments against conspiracy narratives. Such measures contribute to the perpetuation of trust (see [Nurture trust in public health communication](#)) in medical and democratic systems, and help to raise the number of persons who are willing to be vaccinated (see [Vaccination measures](#)).

Volunteers and social care workers interviewed in the STEP_UP project stated that the positive results of the measures included the fact that some people could be calmed down and that perception of how dangerous the pandemic really was developed. On the other hand, interviewees stated that on the main anti-disinformation had an impact on those people who already believed in the preventive measures.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Be guided by scientific evidence and trustworthy sources to recognise disinformation.
- If you come across targeted disinformation, take action to counteract.
- On an individual level, for example, it is possible to report posts on social media and block them.
- If you have the resources, hire a small team to detect disinformation.
- If you have the resources, start a campaign to prevent disinformation. For example, you could start a page on social media targeting local disinformation and conspiracy theories. Another possibility would be to draft information leaflets and distribute them in your area.

Don'ts

- Do not trust unofficial information that you have not verified and be guided by scientific findings.
- Do not think that misinformation is obviously recognisable as such and always draw attention to it when you come across false facts.

Anti-disinformation measures in practice

EU: In September 2020, the European Parliament set up a special committee to detect and combat foreign cyberattacks used to distribute misinformation on COVID-19. The European Commission asked online platforms to work closely with independent fact-checkers and provide monthly reports on their efforts to combat fake news. According to the European Commission, positive results have already been seen.

Portugal: In order to counter disinformation, the National Agency for Emergencies and Civil Protection (ANEPC) and the General Directorate of Health in Portugal sent SMS alerts with trustworthy information to citizens. In addition, the Portuguese Ministry of Internal Affairs distributed information leaflets to adequately inform the population and prevent infections.

The Netherlands: In 2020, the Netherlands issued an NL-Alert (on people's mobile phones) to remind citizens of the main rules for preventing the spread of coronavirus and tackling disinformation. The alert was sent out throughout the Netherlands by the National Crisis Centre in The Hague and was also displayed on many digital billboards and departure time displays used in public transport.³⁸

Communication Measures

Institutionalise communication and tailor strategies for different target groups

Description and possible impact

Institutional facilities for communications provide an essential infrastructure to support non-medical interventions during a pandemic. In this context, it is important to state clearly which institutions disseminate valid information, and establish fixed facilities like telephone hotlines or set consistent times for new announcements. Sometimes countries without communication units have struggled to deliver consistent information over time or update citizens swiftly on how pandemic guidelines might be changing. On the other hand, institutionalisation of communication in governmental facilities guarantees the necessary resources and innovative capabilities to deploy novel tools and services, prepare accurate information and publish compelling data visualisations.

In this context, it is important to keep in mind that, for communication purposes, the general public does not exist as a unit but as a combination of sub-groups. Women, older adults, adolescents, youths, children, persons with disabilities, indigenous populations, refugees, migrants, and minorities may experience the highest degree of socio-economic marginalisation and are therefore likely to become more vulnerable in emergencies.³⁹ Diverse social and economic contexts, vulnerabilities, different life experiences as well as demographics require communicators to adopt tailored approaches. Inequalities in access to information and literacy also require different communication tools and channels because groups with varying levels of ICT skills and disparate approaches to health-related activities experienced the pandemic differently.⁴⁰

Municipality officials interviewed as part of the STEP_UP project cited a better social understanding of this measure given the positive results obtained after its implementation. On the other hand, respondents pointed out that institutionalised communication should always take place in connection with the right partners. They criticised the fact that, although various States worked together with influencers to strengthen different prevention measures, these influencers contradicted the interventions at later stages of the pandemic because, for example, they decided to travel.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Depoliticise health communication by putting health officials at the centre of communications.
- Create a pandemic communication unit.
- Limit the number of institutions/people delivering messages.
- Innovate around new communications technologies, e.g., chatbots to answer questions.
- Ensure that messages are sensitive to demographics and socio-economic and cultural background of the intended targets, e.g., tailor messages for older adults, including for illiterate people, and make them actionable for particular living and health circumstances.
- Ensure translation of key messages and materials in the languages that people understand.
- Select appropriate channels and tools.
- Engage with social influencers, such as religious leaders, to prompt reflection on people who are stigmatised and how to support them. Involve respected celebrities to amplify messages that reduce stigma.
- Disseminate information that uses clear, inclusive and simple language and accessible formats.

Don'ts

- Use geographic/ethnicity labels (e.g., 'Wuhan Virus')
- Forget the fact that public health information pertains to everyone but make sure you reach marginalised and/or vulnerable communities, without labelling them specifically.

Institutionalised and tailored communication in practice

United Kingdom: The Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport has launched a campaign to tackle false vaccine information shared amongst ethnic minority communities, providing a toolkit with content designed to be shared via WhatsApp and Facebook community groups, as well as Twitter, YouTube and Instagram. The campaign is fronted by trusted local community figures such as religious leaders, clinicians and others who provide simple tips on how to spot misinformation and what to do to stop its spread in short, shareable videos.⁴¹ A full social media toolkit for background information and suggested social media posts are also provided.

Sweden: The COVID-19 centre on the City of Stockholm's website provided updated coronavirus information in over 10 languages as well as sign languages. The city also provided a multilingual telephone service for citizens who had additional questions. This translation work was ultimately focused on fostering unity and provided increased access to government guidance to foreign residents and international migrants beyond the Swedish language.

Denmark: The country has been able to re-open schools safely while keeping infection rates low due to institutionalised collaboration between schools (and their personnel) and government offices. To support local schools as designated responsible entities for executing policies, the Danish Ministry of Health established a telephone hotline to answer questions on how to enforce country-level protocols. The National Board of Health also issued a guide specifically designed for schools, teachers and other educators. The guide ensured general understanding of the policies and compliance across the several actors involved in the process.⁴²

Communication Measures

Foster public engagement

Description and possible impacts

Collaborating with citizens and civil society may create a more robust response; in turn, listening and responding to citizens' problems and concerns strengthens democratic values such as solidarity and collective responsibility. One of the key objectives of a successful communication strategy is to ensure that effective feedback mechanisms are in place and used to ensure two-way communication between health/response authorities and communities, the general public and stakeholders. Examples of implementation could be internet forums or question and answer portals where citizens can express their fears and problems.

Municipality officials interviewed in the STEP_UP project stated that, by applying this measure, cooperation between politicians, experts and citizens would be promoted and social dispersion of disease could be prevented at an early stage. Moreover, respondents stated that in future pandemic situations, direct exchanges from society to institutions and decision makers need to be facilitated.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Engage the general public in raising awareness.
- Use messengers who are trusted by target audience.
- Amplify public voices by giving visibility to testimonials, ground workers, etc.
- Implement social listening and community feedback systems.

Anti-disinformation measures in practice

United Kingdom: Portsmouth City Council (2021) looked for community members to become champions and support the roll-out of the COVID-19 vaccination programme to ensure everyone was receiving trusted and up-to-date information about the vaccine.

Estonia: The Community App of the Estonian municipality of Järva Vald is an online digital community hosting a public discussion forum, an RSS feed and a calendar with community events. During the worst times of lockdown measures, its users continuously received 'infocards' with the most up to date COVID-19 information and the legislation applicable in their community. The app thus opened a reliable communication channel between residents and their municipality.⁴³

SOCIAL MEASURES

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Social Measures

After having been introduced to communication measures in the first chapter, the following section deals with social measures. Their implementation is not limited to a specific sector and they show how everyone, regardless of their profession, can make a valuable and solidarity-based contribution to the containment of transmissible diseases.

Some of the following measures focused more on health care at the beginning of the pandemic but, as the number of infections increased, their social significance became increasingly clear. An example of this can be found in the testing measures (see [Testing measures](#)). At the beginning of the pandemic, testing was only possible when there had been direct contact with infected persons and only in a clinical context. In the meantime, the importance of each individual's actions in society during pandemics has become increasingly clear and tests are available for purchase in all supermarkets. In countries like Germany and Portugal, for example, every citizen could take a free test every week or a specific number of tests per month in 2021.⁴⁴

The measures that are outlined in this section offer easy-to-use strategies for everyone. Simple but effective prevention measures, such as wearing masks or keeping a safe distance (see [Preventive measures](#)), testing (see [Testing measures](#)) and isolation measures (see [Quarantine / Self-isolation](#)) are discussed. In combination with the right level of risk awareness, they act as effective means against the spread of diseases.

Suggested events including social measures in the STEP_UP educational game

Event 17

Help **Katharina Fisher**, the head of the Neighbourhood Initiative, to implement preventive measures and share needed equipment to support vulnerable people.

Preventive measures

Event 16

Help **Rosa Santos** to organise a testing campaign and isolate infected people.

Testing measures

Quarantine /
Isolation measures

Event 24

Help **Dr. Francis Nelson** to provide official recommendations about prevention measures when the number of active cases is decreasing.

Preventive measures

[CLICK HERE TO ACCESS THE STEP_UP GAME](#)

Description

A decisive role in the fight against communicable diseases is played by individually implemented preventive measures such as increased hygiene, appropriate social distancing, or use of face masks. These three measures will be highlighted as they allow everyone to play an active role in limiting the spread of the virus.

At the beginning of the pandemic outbreak, **masks** were only mandatory for infected people and caregivers.⁴⁵ However, as the pandemic progressed, it became clear that they were having a major impact on society, reducing the spread of the virus. One of the reasons for this is that the coronavirus is transmitted via aerosols in the air and thus via the respiratory tract.⁴⁶ Wearing masks is recommended in acute pandemic situations for the whole of society. They also promote a sense of solidarity. In any case, they should be worn by people with symptoms, infected people, care workers and people close to infected people.

Another key preventive measure during the pandemic was **social distancing** which had already been recommended by the WHO since the beginning of the pandemic.⁴⁷ The unit of measurement for distance regulations is about 1.5 metres, although some countries recommend one or two metres. In addition, it was suggested to reduce the number of people allowed in the same indoor space and to set up barriers (for example Plexiglas) to make virus transmission more difficult.

Since the virus spreads via droplet infection, residues of the virus can also remain on surfaces. Therefore, it became clear that **hygiene measures** such as washing hands or cleaning surfaces are essential to contain the spread of a virus.⁴⁸ Hands should be washed several times a day and dried with paper towels. In addition, hands should be disinfected regularly, just like used or frequently touched surfaces that could have been touched by an infected person.

In addition to the prevention measures mentioned above, there are of course other measures, such as ventilation for indoor air exchange, self-isolation in case of suspected illness (see [Quarantine / Self-isolation](#)) and regular testing for illnesses (see [Testing measures](#)).

By whom and where can it be applied?

The prevention measures mentioned above can be applied by all parts of society at different levels. Thus, everyone can use the measures individually to show solidarity even if they are not ill; political institutions can make them mandatory. Moreover, businesses have the opportunity to implement the measures in their premises.

Impact

The application of the above-mentioned measures in society as a whole has a major impact on controlling communicable diseases. For example, a large number of studies suggest that wearing masks in combination with hygiene measures significantly reduces the spread of respiratory diseases.⁴⁹ In addition to cleaning one's hands, the positive effect of cleaning surfaces has also been proven.⁵⁰ Furthermore, social distancing has a restrictive effect on communicable diseases. An American model study from the year 2020 concluded that moderate implementation throughout America could have saved nearly 1 million lives and the utilisation of intensive care beds could have been drastically reduced.⁵¹

Healthcare professionals and healthcare workers interviewed in the STEP_UP project cited lower infection rates for various diseases as a positive outcome of this measure. In addition, they mentioned improved understanding of hygiene and ease of use as positive aspects. On the other hand, they pointed out that in some circumstances, such as in the open air, the measures were unnecessarily adopted and that more information needs to be given in the media to prevent potentially divergent opinions on them.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Wear a mask to protect yourself and your fellow citizens in pandemic situations. It is better to use an FFP-2 mask than a simple surgical mask as it has a higher protection factor.
- Wash your hands regularly during the day as this reduces the spread of communicable diseases. Wash your hands with soap for at least 20 seconds to ensure adequate hygiene.
- Disinfect frequently used surfaces regularly.
- In acute pandemic situations, stay at least one meter away from other people to avoid direct contact.

Don'ts

- Do not be confused by unreliable media reports. Stick to official reports and apply the prevention measures that are compulsory in your country of residence.

Preventive measures in practice

In **Germany**, the government recommended compliance with the 'AHA' rules from 8 June 2020, where A stands for masks (*Alltagsmasken*), H for Hygiene and A for social distancing (*Abstand*).⁵²

Description

An innovation in the fight against the coronavirus were tracing apps, which offer health authorities support in tracking infection chains. They are designed to allow users to detect contact with infected people over their mobile phones at an earlier stage and to make it possible to isolate themselves. To be effective, tracing apps must be available for voluntary download, and should be free of charge and downloaded by around 60% of the population.⁵³ More details on contact tracing besides tracing apps can be found under [Contact tracing](#).

By downloading the app and using technologies such as **GPS** or distance measurement via **Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE)**, societal infections should be recorded automatically, and individual users should be informed as soon as there is an excessive risk of illness in certain locations or too many people with high infection rates around users.

In addition to mobile technologies, the type of data storage plays an invaluable role in raising trust towards tracing apps, especially because this is an important factor in increasing acceptance and use of tracing apps.⁵⁴ With regard to data storage, there are **'centralised' systems** which are based on long-term national preservation of information in one (central) governmental location that is intended to be used in further epidemiological evaluations.

On the other hand, there are also **'decentralised' ways of storage** with data directly saved on users' smartphones for a maximum of, for example, 14 days.⁵⁵ As this type of storage complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), it is also recommended by the European Union. In this context, the European Commission even provided an interoperable system to which the various national tracing apps can be connected that also ensures international control within the EU and facilitates travelling. The graph below shows the current state of use of tracing apps in Europe.⁵⁶

Tracing apps in the EU. Source: https://ec.europa.eu/info/live-work-travel-eu/coronavirus-response/travel-during-coronavirus-pandemic/how-tracing-and-warning-apps-can-help-during-pandemic_en

By whom and where can it be applied?

The measure can be carried out and supported at any time by anyone who has a smartphone with GPS or Bluetooth.

Impact

The impact of tracing apps heavily depends on the degree of societal application and consensus, as downloading is voluntary in most European countries and the full impact of the apps only emerges through a **network effect**. The decisive factor is therefore the percentage of the population that actively uses the app and has activated all crucial technologies such as Bluetooth or GPS. Results of a model study by the University of Oxford indicate that, with an extensive app use by about 60% of the population, the number of COVID-19 cases and associated hospitalisations could already be significantly reduced.⁵⁷

Social workers and volunteers who have been interviewed in the framework of the STEP_UP project mentioned as positive outcomes of the measure an increased personal risk perception, faster disease detection and quicker likelihood of isolating infected persons. In contrast, they criticised insufficient data protection and a less user-friendly design, which can also exclude certain groups such as older adults. Furthermore, they complained about lack of communication and information regarding the app and stated that the app signals can often be blocked in closed rooms, which can limit their functionality.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- The user interface should be as simple and unambiguous as possible to ensure that the apps are actually used.
- Support groups such as older adults who are less familiar with the functionality of smartphones and apps.
- The benefits of tracing apps need to be communicated very clearly in order to increase its efficacy through its voluntary use.
- If data protection is important to you, choose an app where anonymised data will be stored and only shared with health authorities.
- Use this measure in combination with other contact tracing methods (see *Contact tracing*).

Don'ts

- Do not rely on unsafe or high energy consuming technologies that drain phone batteries as this will reduce the apps usage.
- Personal data stored in the apps should not be disclosed for purposes other than contact tracing to ensure that users feel safe in sharing their private data.
- Do not choose an app with a complicated design as this may exclude certain groups such as older adults.

Tracing apps in practice

In **South Korea**, tracing apps such as 'Corona 100' enjoy wide social approval and have been able to make a major contribution to speeding up contact tracing. Among other things, it has shown that movement tracking of infected people could be accelerated from 24 hours to about 10 minutes. The success of the Korean tracing app also depends on the population's overwhelming support. One reason for this approval could be the MERS outbreak in 2015 which, to a certain extent, prepared South Koreans for the current emergency situation. On the other hand, this outbreak has also led to legislative relief in terms of data protection, which means that the data and travel histories of app users can be treated less confidentially. The government has chosen to give precedence to social good over individual privacy rights.⁵⁸

Description

Once a new pathogen is investigated, it is important to determine the best method to identify the virus. There are multiple components that need to be considered when using testing as a measure to help control the spread of a virus. There are different types of tests like **ART (Antigen Rapid Tests)**, less reliable but giving results faster, and more accurate **PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) tests**, which need much longer to be evaluated. Molecular tests, such as real-time PCR, have been the most common laboratory tools used to detect cases of COVID-19 and have become an integral part of a multi-component strategy aimed at reducing transmission of the virus.⁵⁹ Accordingly, testing was essential in the contact tracing measure (see [Contact tracing](#)) and was also used to assess quarantine situations (see [Quarantine / Self-isolation](#)). Furthermore, they played a role in the safety of hospitals,⁶⁰ especially as some facilities even set up separate testing centres (see [Establish an isolation ward](#)) at their entrances. Since the role of testing changes constantly during pandemics, it is necessary to regularly adapt this measure to the current situation. As a result, enforcement can also vary between voluntary and mandatory testing.

By whom and where can it be applied?

Test measures are carried out in all kinds of places and play a crucial role in monitoring current circumstances, responding to problems, and enforcing other measures such as quarantines or bans on hospital visits. The enforcement of testing measures varied greatly during the pandemic. For example, at the beginning, this measure was only used by medical professionals in cases of illness. However, as the pandemic progressed, self-testing also played an increasing role, and tests could be bought in supermarkets by all groups of society.

Impact

Testing is required to monitor the COVID-19 pandemic (giving information on the reproduction number, i.e., the number of cases generated from one case, and enabling the identification of the extent of transmission). An important contribution to the prevention of transmission through testing is made by populations at high risk of acquiring infection and transmitting it to vulnerable people, like healthcare and social care workers.⁶¹ However, it should be noted that the true impact of testing in terms of virus containment is mainly in the context of other measures. For example, testing is necessary to isolate people in quarantine (see [Quarantine / Self-isolation](#)), to interrupt infection chains through contact tracing (see [Contact tracing](#)) and to justify possible opening measures at the end of the pandemic. Therefore, tests play a role in the overall course of disease outbreaks and make a consistently valuable contribution to virus control.⁶² On top of their direct benefit for the healthcare sector, they are important to support the whole society in enforcing self-isolation. Ultimately, they are necessary for organisational purposes as existing measures can be adapted based on the spread of the virus and new measures can be developed.⁶³

Healthcare workers and professionals interviewed within the STEP_UP project named increased personal responsibility through self-testing, detection before the occurrence of symptoms and thus a reduction in the prevalence as positive results of this measure. On the other hand, they criticised the partly inconsistent societal enforcement of testing and, in some cases, a lack of information on why extensive testing is needed.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Try to implement testing measures as widely as possible, but be aware of the available resources, such as personnel and test availability, and the number of people requiring a test.
- Create higher and lower priority streams for faster sample collection and test processing when capacity is limited.
- Offer tests free of charge during peak periods of illness and make them available for private use to achieve a higher level of social self-regulation.

Don'ts

- Do not wait too long to implement this measure. Above all, testing measures must be implemented right at the beginning of a pandemic to protect systemically important groups such as nurses.
- Do not take the relevance of testing for granted and inform all social groups why it is essential to be tested regularly for virus control.

Testing measures in practice

After initially allowing testing only in a medical context, most **European countries** converted their virus surveillance using freely available and purchasable tests, allowing larger segments of the population to be screened.⁶⁴

On the way to holistic social testing that is not exclusively institutional, solutions such as test drive-throughs or self-testing at kiosks also contributed to making self-screening a routine practice.⁶⁵

Test drive-through. Source: [Delaware National Guard offers COVID-19 testing in Millsboro](#) | Flickr

Social Measures

Quarantine / Self-isolation

Description

Isolation and quarantine help protect the public by preventing exposure to people who have or may have a contagious disease, such as persons who have had contacts with infected people or with people arriving from countries perceived as risk areas. **Isolation** separates sick people with a contagious disease from those who are not sick whereas **Quarantine** separates and restricts the movement of people who were exposed to a contagious disease to see if they become sick. Most important in the implementation of quarantine and isolation measures is to use them in conjunction with testing measures (see [Testing measures](#)). This is needed to identify an infection and to be sure when starting a quarantine.⁶⁶

The duration of quarantine and isolation depends on the infectious disease. For Sars-CoV-2 it is about 14 days from the onset of symptoms or from a positive test if the person is asymptomatic.⁶⁷ Throughout the course of the epidemic, some countries adjusted and shortened the quarantine/self-isolation periods due to knowledge about the spread of the virus, larger vaccination capacities, and economic reasons.

Quarantine and isolation measures are often mandatory or recommended with reference to individual responsibility. Moreover, there are specific instructions on how to properly isolate yourself from the people you live with. These include ensuring that you have a space where you can live on your own for the necessary number of days with adequate food and water supply as well as the use of a bathroom. If there is a need to be in the same room as other members of the household, physical distancing is advised along with wearing a mask and disinfecting commonly used areas.⁶⁸

By whom and where can it be applied?

Target groups of this measure are individuals who have tested positive and their contacts in the general population. Quarantine and self-isolation measures are strongly related to testing and communication measures in a disease outbreak. Initially, quarantines were medically prescribed, and only certain people could be tested. As the disease outbreak progressed, tests became more widely available thanks to testing stations or because they were on sale in supermarkets. The decision to test and the potential subsequent quarantine also depended on society's perception of danger and consequently on health communication in the media.⁶⁹

Impact

For centuries quarantine and isolation have been effective measures to combat the spread of infectious diseases. These measures reduce the number of new infections, deaths and the viral load thus leading to a better control of the epidemic. The negative consequences that these measures can have on individuals in isolation are psychological: emotional disturbance, depression, stress, low mood and irritability among others.⁷⁰ Quarantine and isolation measures can also have negative impacts on the economy because people cannot go to work. The scope of this pandemic has had repercussions especially on those who cannot use home office solutions. A further problem also arises for voluntary and social care, as those carrying out this type of work often must put themselves at risk when providing support to isolated people who need it. For these individuals adopting preventive measures, like using protective equipment and social distancing, is absolutely necessary (see [Preventive measures](#)).⁷¹

Volunteers and social care workers interviewed within the STEP_UP project mentioned an increased sense of security and a delayed spread of the virus as advantages of this measure, as all infected persons were isolated. On the other hand, respondents demanded more control over implementation and free home delivery of tests, so that people could test themselves before finishing the quarantine period. Furthermore, it became clear that the 14-day quarantine period was clearly too long for most people. However, as the average incubation period for Sars-CoV-2 is approximately 6 days, a minimum of 10 days' isolation is needed to prevent spreading, depending on the virus variant. Lastly, some respondents stated that there was too little communication about the quarantine measures and their importance to ensure effective social enforcement.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Check the quarantine regulations in force in your country of residence to ensure compliance with all rules.
- While in quarantine, check your symptoms regularly to be able to react quickly in case of a severe progression of the disease.
- While in quarantine, stay away from other people, including your flatmates, and follow preventive measures to avoid infecting anyone (see [Preventive measures](#)).
- Ventilate your rooms frequently, as some disease viruses, such as the coronavirus, are transmitted via aerosols in the air.

Don'ts

- Do not leave your home during quarantine unless it is an absolute emergency.
- Do not go to sport events, religious meetings or use public transport during quarantine.
- Do not meet other people until your quarantine or isolation period is over.

Quarantine in practice

An example of how quarantine was implemented in practice and how its enforcement was monitored is provided by **Taiwan**: all suspected Corona cases or those entering the country from risk areas had to spend 14 days in a digitally monitored quarantine environment. They were entitled to a daily allowance of 30 euros and had to provide a mobile phone number (or received a mobile phone if they did not have one). Afterwards, radio cell tracking was used to ensure that the individual actually was at the quarantine location. In addition, several daily calls were made to check whether the person was in the immediate proximity of the mobile phone. Finally, in case of non-compliance with the rules, penalty notices were sent by SMS to ensure that the quarantine was respected.⁷²

CARE MEASURES

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The measures described in this chapter relate to the **healthcare** and **social care** sectors and how their working environments had to adjust and adapt to improve control over the spread of COVID-19. Sources range from studies and analyses published in academic journals to other scientific and public online sources like social media posts. In addition, a survey within the framework of the STEP_UP project among affected professional groups from the healthcare sector was used to identify positive results achieved through the measures and to generate first-hand suggestions for improvement. The communication and social measures that have already been presented also play an important role in supporting care interventions. In the following section, however, specific measures for the healthcare sector are discussed.

Outbreaks of newly emerging or re-emerging infectious diseases present a unique challenge and a threat to healthcare providers (HCPs) and other frontline responders. This is due to the limited understanding of the emerging threat and reliance on infection prevention and control (IPC) measures that may not consider all transmission dynamics of the emerging pathogens. It was one of the first times in recent history that healthcare professionals were faced with a respiratory virus that could spread quickly and affect every country in the world. Researchers needed time to catch up with data and evidence which would help combat the disease and control outbreaks while considering all other social, economic, and psychological aspects which people may encounter. While the pandemic has placed unparalleled demands on healthcare systems, it has also indirectly brought about new innovations to help caring for entire populations.

The measures for the Care sector described in this chapter include measures introduced on the basis of prior knowledge about respiratory pathogens which have been adapted for the purposes of Sars-CoV-2 as we have learned more about the epidemiology of the disease. One of the first crucial steps in managing the epidemic in each country was an effective and thorough way of identifying and confirming positive Sars-CoV-2 cases and track these (see [Contact tracing](#)).⁷³ One of the first measures introduced was testing using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) to confirm the symptomatic and asymptomatic presence of the virus (see [Testing measures](#)). Following the positive identification of a case epidemiologic history is necessary to further isolate any close contacts and slow down the potential spread of the disease. This is vital to control the spread of disease, quarantine positive patients and isolate their contacts.⁷⁴ As the pandemic progressed, researchers were mobilised quickly and efficiently, and created vaccines for COVID-19 (see [Vaccination measures](#)) which would change the landscape of the pandemic once countries began rolling out national programmes.⁷⁵ The high human and economic costs associated with COVID-19 make it more important than ever to accelerate and scale medical innovations rapidly. Healthcare leaders should consider providing the tools, processes, and capabilities their teams are likely to need to move quickly while ensuring that patient safety and quality of care remain central. A short list of organisational guidelines for the healthcare sector can be found below.

Organisational guidelines in healthcare:

- Design a rapid assessment of HCWs with symptoms compatible with COVID-19
- Develop plans for the safe participation of support staff in patient care, especially for labour, delivery, and postpartum support.
- Prepare to cancel or scale back on services of an elective or less urgent nature.
- Stockpile essential equipment and supplies including medications (see [Financial resources / subsidies](#)).
- Develop plans to increase space and staffing, especially for medical wards and critical care services, and develop plans for training HCWs who will be performing unfamiliar roles.
- Focus on keeping non-COVID-19 hospital wards and services COVID-19 free (see [Establish an isolation ward](#)).
- Identify measures to mitigate hospital crowding such as standardising admission and discharge criteria.
- Plan effective communication (see [Communication Measures](#)).

Aside from the healthcare sector, the social care sector has also been greatly affected by COVID-19. This is a sector that cares for millions of people who are dependent on services offered to them every day. It is crucial that the social sector makes the most of its resources, coordinating between professionals from different municipalities, cooperatives or associations. Social services and organisations have innovated by launching social and emotional support telephone services (see *Institutionalise communication and tailor strategies for different target groups*), especially for people with mental health problems whose circumstances have exacerbated during the pandemic and in light of new cases. Like the healthcare sector, the social care sector had to adjust and change protocols and guidelines to keep one of the most at-risk populations safe and healthy. Measures which needed to be taken in these settings were based on guidelines adopted by public health institutes to help ensure safety and allow work to flow as smoothly as possible.

Older adults living in congregate settings are at high risk of being affected by respiratory and other pathogens, such as SARS-CoV-2. A strong infection prevention and control (IPC) programme is critical to protect both residents and healthcare workers. Care homes and other social services working with populations at a greater risk must sustain core IPC practices and remain vigilant for SARS-CoV-2 infection among residents and HCW to prevent spread and protect residents and HCW from severe infections, hospitalisations, and death. During the COVID-19 crisis, the social care sector has faced one of the most challenging times because it had to cover urgent social needs in an uncertain scenario. Next to the measures that will be explained in detail in the following pages, there are general guidelines for their use, which help reduce the spread of infection and are used in line with all traditional evidence-based medicine and infection control measures for these settings.

Organisational guidelines in social care:

- Visitors to social care institutions must sign a statement before making direct contact with patients declaring that they do not have raised temperature or respiratory symptoms and that, to their knowledge, they have not been in contact with an infected person.
- Take the temperature of visitors and workers before they enter the premises of a social centre.
- At the entrance to the premises of a social centre, visitors and workers must disinfect hands (see *Preventive measures*).
- After the reception desk has checked their statements and taken their temperature, new patients should enter the hospital one by one.
- A special room must be provided at reception where new patients will be received without making contact with other potential patients or visitors.
- Whenever possible patients arrive at the agreed time, they should be able to wait for their turn in an open space; after their appointment or procedure, they should not be kept in the centre for longer than necessary.
- Professionals working in the admissions office should take turns. After three hours of work, a one-hour break must be provided. During changes, the areas they are using should be disinfected.
- Wherever possible, ensure that no more than two professionals work in the same room to avoid infection.
- Visits to patients' families are performed in all situations when necessary and in accordance with the rules of the profession and using protective equipment.
- Visits to patients' homes should be kept as short as possible and all activities carried out at their homes should comply with the rules of the institution.
- Social care institutions or informal care facilities should work with local organisations, businesses or government bodies to acquire more resources and more targeted assistance to better address vulnerable people like older adults, children or people requiring care.⁷⁶

Suggested events including care measures in the STEP_UP educational game

Event 4

Help **Rosa Santos** to help and support nursing staff.

Increase staff and conduct trainings for staff performing unfamiliar tasks

Event 5

Help **Dr. Pedro Jimenez** to control unnecessary visits to hospitals.

Establish an isolation ward

Event 6

Help **Dr. Francis Nelson** to put the best possible contact tracing strategy in place.

Contact tracing

[CLICK HERE TO ACCESS THE STEP_UP GAME](#)

Description

The WHO defines contact tracing as the process of identifying, assessing, and managing people who have been exposed to a disease to prevent onward transmission. It is a focused method that targets people who have had potentially infectious interactions with people suffering from a transmittable disease. Therefore, after an infected person has been confirmed positive and been isolated, their entire social environment will also be contacted to break chains of infection and consequently contain the disease.⁷⁷

According to the WHO, there are five key components of contact tracing: a workforce which is trained in contact tracing; support from the public and community engagement; thorough planning while taking into account local contexts; logistics to help support teams; and a platform where data can be entered, stored and further analysed in real time.⁷⁸ Health authorities are usually responsible for the disease identification work with this platform; all citizens must be taken into account and, above all, the periods of action play a role. Periods of action are especially oriented towards the incubation period of a disease since isolation before the outbreak has the greatest effect.⁷⁹

Contact tracing works on different levels: **individual and societal level**, where individuals are tested and larger chains of infection should be broken, and **medical and scientific level**, where, after being collected, data is evaluated to identify risk factors and transmission methods for society as a whole and taken into account for further measures.⁸⁰

Digital technologies are playing an increasingly important role both at individual level and at the level of medical action. One innovation, for example, are tracing apps (see [Tracing Apps](#)) as they enable everybody to support contact tracing and simplify transmission of information for health authorities. 'Syndromic surveillance' can be mentioned for the medical level: this technology uses algorithms and infection-related data to improve the classification of mass gatherings' infectious effects.⁸¹

By whom and where can it be applied?

In many countries contact tracing is performed by trained staff such as doctors, nurses, pharmacists, medical students, retired doctors, public health professionals and volunteers. Contact tracing has been mainly done through phone calls where the contact tracer identifies everyone the person has been in contact with while potentially being infectious. Moreover, digital technologies have become increasingly important as demonstrated by tracing apps.⁸²

Impact

Contact tracing has been identified as a key element to control the spread of COVID-19. It is important to have good contact tracing strategies in place. Additional resources must be invested to ensure that this measure can be thoroughly implemented. Therefore, test measures are extremely important (see [Testing measures](#)) because otherwise no positive individuals can be identified. However, even if countries have the appropriate resources to perform contact tracing, the most important requirements for successful case management are the ability of the system to identify potential cases quickly as well as adequate monitoring and management of contacts. Most countries have adopted a decentralised approach at county/local public health level.⁸³ Thanks to their close connection to the community, this means that individuals can be contacted at local level. However, this approach may have geographical imbalances, as not all authorities have the same workforce or resources to contact all the infected people. In addition to the resources that have been employed, the impact of contact tracing is also very much related to surrounding interventions⁸⁴ such as early detection of infections in primary care by PCR or other equivalent test (see [Testing measures](#)), closer coordination with epidemiological surveillance services, and adherence to general isolation (see [Quarantine / Self-isolation](#)) and prevention measures (see [Preventive measures](#)).

Public health workers and healthcare professionals who were interviewed in the STEP_UP project mentioned improved risk awareness and targeted information for those affected by the virus as positive results of this measure. However, some interviewees emphasised that contact tracing can only stop infection chains with relatively small numbers but has limited effect when incidence is high. In addition, long tracing periods, as often is the case, were criticised. Therefore, contact tracing is often too slow, and people can infect other people before they are asked by health authorities to self-isolate. Furthermore, mandatory isolation from families can have mental consequences.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Apply contact tracing at the beginning of an outbreak as the effect is highest at this time.
- Seek local support through clubs, institutions, and associations if you are responsible for contact tracing. This can also be important to identify potential gatherings as a source of infection.
- Develop solid structures to shorten the identification time of the virus; this is very important to prevent an infected person from contaminating others before identification.
- Most importantly, contact tracing has to be used in conjunction with other preventive and isolating measures. For example, testing (see [Testing measures](#)) and hygiene in combination with distancing regulations can lead to infected persons and their environment being contacted earlier and transmitting the virus more slowly.

Don'ts

- Do not wait too long to use this measure because it becomes less effective as the number of infections increases.
- Don't just use one method to ask people about their contacts. In addition to the telephone, use direct approaches, information from local clubs and associations, and monitor possible sources of infection.

Contact tracing in practice

Vietnam was very successful in the area of contact tracing. This was partly due to the number of tracking options. For example, location data from Facebook or Instagram posts were used in addition to contacting people by phone. Personal face-to-face tracing was particularly successful. Targeted training on tracing was offered in Vietnam to improve the health system's coverage and significantly reduce the identification time of infected persons.⁸⁵

Care Measures

Establish an isolation ward

Description

Isolation of infected patients in hospitals helps to protect other patients by preventing contact. Therefore, isolation wards in hospitals are a key element. Infected patients are directly transferred to a separate ward that protects both the other patients and the hospital staff through spatial separation. However, to guarantee that everyone's safety is considered, several additional measures are required. For example, air cleaning devices are needed on the ceilings to prevent airborne transmission of pathogens.⁸⁶ In addition, personal measures, such as the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) by healthcare workers and compliance with distancing regulations as well as other preventive measures (see [Preventive measures](#)) for visitors, play an important role to guarantee the success of COVID-19 wards. Coloured floor markings are often used to support compliance with distancing regulations.⁸⁷

By whom and where can it be applied?

Building COVID-19 isolation wards is a political decision imposed on hospitals; hospitals with fever wards are usually selected first. The care and health services in the wards are still left to healthcare workers and professionals, such as nurses and doctors, which is why personal protection measures such as distancing and protective equipment play such an important role.

Impact

The influence of isolation wards on disease containment is, as explained above, strongly dependent on the additional spatial or individual preventive measures that in most cases are compulsory. However, isolation wards are indispensable for the safety of hospital processes. On the other hand, the extra wards have added to the workers' workload considerably as demonstrated by the constant change of protective clothing. To minimise the amount of time spent on new procedures, training staff can be useful (see *Increase staff and conduct trainings for employees performing unfamiliar tasks*).⁸⁸

Contrary to the positive effects in terms of virus containment, staying in isolation wards can cause enormous psychological stress for patients because of lack of family contact, growing insecurity due to the disease and, often, lack of psychological support. This is caused by the fact that in many isolation wards people are isolated in single rooms. To improve this situation, technological devices or bedside telephones, among other things, can be used to reach both hospital staff and one's personal environment.⁸⁹ Isolation hoods can also be a solution as they allow to have several people in a room, and constant eye contact with hospital staff and other patients is possible to prevent loneliness.⁹⁰

Healthcare workers and professionals interviewed as part of the STEP_UP project cited a greatly reduced spread of the virus in hospitals and an increased level of control and protection as positive results. On the other hand, they criticised the fact that the new wards might have initially led to a reduced quality of treatment in hospitals.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Consider the problem of loneliness and try to provide patients with entertainment and opportunities for contacts through digital devices.
- Use this measure in conjunction with other preventive and protective measures to prevent the spread of the virus in hospitals. Also, try to ensure that certain personnel always work on the same stations, so as not to transfer the virus between them.
- Require or encourage training opportunities that are specifically designed to prepare professionals to work in isolation wards.

Don'ts

- Do not wait too long to apply the measure. Already in the early outbreak phase, it is important to ensure that other patients are not infected.
- Make sure that the increased organisation and workload is not at the expense of the usual treatment methods, and offer training to prepare employees (see *Increase staff and conduct trainings for employees performing unfamiliar tasks*).

Isolation wards in practice

Isolation wards can be visited in many hospitals. Among other things, the principle of **mobile isolation wards** has already been introduced in **China**. These are set up in containers or tents for little money. They also serve as testing stations, and affiliated hospitals can share resources. Mobile isolation wards could make a decisive contribution to the successful management of the pandemic in China and increase treatment capabilities.⁹¹

Care Measures

Increase staff and conduct trainings for employees performing unfamiliar tasks

Description

One of the main problems during the corona pandemic was a **shortage of personnel**, which mainly affected stationary care. In this exceptional situation, it became clear that the general staffing ratio for nursing professions in hospitals was too low. Cooperation with temporary employment agencies was often a solution to cope with the increased workload due to mandatory preventive measures such as protective clothing and work in isolation wards.⁹² Even if temporary employment agencies can relieve permanent staff to a certain extent, the problem of staff shortages will be aggravated in the future by a demographic change within the nursing labour force.⁹³ In Germany, for example, there has already been a persistent shortage of skilled workers for a number of years, which is also related to a lack of young professionals. Even if the arrangement with temporary employment agencies is helpful, political solutions will be necessary in the long term such as, for example, better salaries to potential young carers.⁹⁴

As a solution to counter this increasing shortage of skilled workers in emergency situations, special **training for health care** staff can help to increase work effectiveness and improve the quality of unfamiliar tasks (for example those performed in an isolation ward).⁹⁵ For example, a Pakistani study has found that training health workers in the use of specialised equipment significantly reduces the spread of a disease within a hospital, which is also linked to a change in the health workers' risk perception.⁹⁶

By whom and where can it be applied?

Reinforcing staff levels through temporary employment agencies as well as organising specific training in the use of protective clothing or new forms of organisation is the responsibility of hospital management. Such targeted training should usually be carried out by in-house experts. In addition, finding new staff is also related to political processes because external staff cannot be considered a permanent solution. A political change towards caregivers, for example in terms of salary, is required to change the situation in the long run.⁹⁷

Impact

In terms of its impact, replenishing the labour force through temporary employment agencies serves as a source of relief to deal with greatly increased staffing needs in pandemic situations. This has a positive impact, especially because workers can perform their tasks with less stress and greater diligence. Even though temporary employment agencies can relieve permanent staff to some extent, it is clear that this will not solve the problems forever. There is also a demographic problem, especially in care, with many workers about to leave their jobs because of their age.⁹⁸ This means that in the long term the problem of staff shortages must also be solved politically. Associations and labour unions are demanding in particular an upgrade in terms of image and better wages in order to launch training programmes and find future generations of workers.⁹⁹

In order to manage staff shortages, another approach would be to adapt existing workers to the changing circumstances through special training and increase their efficiency and ability to work.¹⁰⁰ This approach offers a lot of benefits, such as perceived lower stress levels and a clear understanding of the preventive measures and procedures to be used. Training can also lead to increased risk perception of workers and has been shown to reduce the transmission of diseases within different facilities.¹⁰¹ When implementing training programmes, it is also advisable to use a mixture of online and face-to-face training, with introductory videos and texts accelerating practical learning.¹⁰²

Consistent with this, healthcare professionals and healthcare workers surveyed within the STEP_UP project cited increased virus prevention, increased danger awareness and better work performance as benefits of training.

Recommendations and guidelines for learners

Dos

- Provide training for nursing staff and healthcare professionals at the onset of disease outbreaks to prepare them adequately for the specifics of the disease and thus ensure a more diligent approach.
- Offer trainings that include online tools such as videos or checklists in addition to practical training sessions. This promotes knowledge absorption and ensures that information can be checked afterwards.
- Update staff knowledge with trainings as new scientific evidence of transmission of the disease becomes available.

Increasing staff in practice

Portugal: In order to have more human resources available for the prevention, containment, mitigation and treatment of the COVID-19 pandemic, Portugal authorised hiring workers on four-month temporary contracts from March 2020.¹⁰³

POLITICAL MEASURES

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Political Measures

This last chapter focuses on the description of political measures to cope with pandemic situations. The measures have been extracted by more than 500 researchers from the CoronaNet database on government responses to the coronavirus for 195 countries. At the time of reporting, this database contained more than 60,000 entries thus providing the most comprehensive and detailed documentation of government policies around the world. In the following chapter, policy measures are presented with examples of measures taken at EU level as well as examples from Croatia, Germany, Portugal and Spain. In many cases, these are either good practices or cover particularly interesting aspects of a specific policy area.

However, one of the most important lessons learned from the recent COVID-19 pandemic is that preparedness is key. Countries in regions such as South Asia and West Africa that experienced a considerable amount of SARS-CoV or Ebola cases in previous decades seem to have been better prepared for specific precautionary measures and behavioural requirements than Europe.¹⁰⁴ Based on this, the following chapter will present some political measures that can be applied regardless of the communicable disease. These measure can help to learn from the past and other countries, thus trying to improve responses in the future.

Suggested events including political measures in the STEP_UP educational game

Event 1

Help Health Minister **Britta Johnson** to decide about rules related to lockdown or building a taskforce, as the country should be isolated.

Building a taskforce

Lockdown

Event 13

Help **Britta Johnson** to enforce compliance with bans on mass gatherings.

Restrictions on mass gatherings

Event 18

Help **Dr. Francis Nelson** to organise a vaccination campaign and to select priority groups for vaccination.

Financial investments / subsidies

Vaccination measures

[CLICK HERE TO ACCESS THE STEP_UP GAME](#)

Political Measures

Building a taskforce

Description

Task forces are used in critical situations to concentrate expertise in one single entity to: a) elaborate recommendations for measures to investigate the crisis and remedy its causes; b) take on coordination of crisis management; and c) communicate the developments to crisis squads. This measure can be implemented by giving new powers to an existing government entity or establishing a new body, bureau, etc.

By whom and where can it be applied?

The establishment of task forces is not related to a specific pandemic. A task force has no specific target group but focuses on performing specific tasks for which it has been set up. A task force can be setup by political organs or also in organisations or clubs, to find the best possible solutions in emergency cases.

Impact

Task forces that are composed of experts from all relevant areas can work more effectively on solutions for critical situations than if these tasks are performed in a decentralised way by several institutions. Their work can impact all areas related to the crisis. Notably, inter-institutional task forces mostly focus on coordination, research, and development activities rather than crisis management.

Building a task force in practice

On 10 September 2020, the **WHO** and the **European Commission** launched the Facilitation Council to strengthen global collaboration on the coronavirus response. The aim was to encourage the development and deployment of vaccines, tests, and treatments against COVID-19 as well as improve health systems.¹⁰⁵

Description

Prevention and treatment of diseases are most important in every pandemic. **Public and private financial resources** may be spent to procure urgently needed safety gears, vaccines (see *Vaccination measures*), etc. Funding research is also used to counter a disease and its impacts. Health resources include masks, hand sanitisers, personal protective equipment (PPE), test kits, ventilators, medicines, vaccines, other health materials, hospitals, doctors, nurses, health volunteers, other health staff, health insurance, health research facilities, public testing facilities, temporary medical centres, or other health infrastructure.

In addition to investments in health equipment, in many countries **compensatory subsidies** also played a role for people who could not go to work or had to close their businesses due to restrictions in the public or business sector. In this context, European support payments were of assistance. Following the coronavirus pandemic, the European Commission invested in SURE loans to assist Member States in addressing sudden increases in public expenditure to preserve employment. Specifically, these loans help to cover the costs directly related to the financing of national short term work schemes and other similar measures. Overall, 19 EU Member States are due to receive a total of €94,3 billion in financial support under SURE, following approval by the Council of the European Union based on a Commission proposal.¹⁰⁶

By whom and where can it be applied?

The provision of health resources is not related to specific pandemics. However, the decision to allocate funds is mostly a political one. As well as governments, organisations or individuals can support citizens through investments and by donating resources. Target groups are medical institutions and professions, patients, people who cannot work, business owners and the general public.

Impact

The provision of **health resources** results in expanded capabilities to prevent diseases and treat patients. Ideally, available health resources should lead to relaxing restrictions and regulations at economic level and in terms of social life and personal relations, as health systems have enough capacity to cope with high rates of infection.

Financial **subsidies** for companies and employees in times of restrictions also have an important impact, especially because they can be essential to maintain a country's economic viability and employment numbers even after the crisis, and prevent it from entering an endless recession.

Investments in health resources in practice

An example of investment in health resources can be found in **Croatia**: as of 20 March 2020, hospital beds were being installed in Zagreb's Arena concert hall for patients who were not in serious conditions. Their transfer was organised when hospital beds had to be freed up for coronavirus patients.¹⁰⁷

Description

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, non-pharmaceutical interventions, colloquially known as lockdowns, were implemented in numerous countries and territories around the world. Lockdowns are generally understood as stay-at-home orders with few exceptions. By April 2020, about half of the world's population was under some form of lockdown, with more than 3.9 billion people in more than 90 countries or territories having been asked or ordered to stay at home by their governments. Although similar disease control measures have been used for hundreds of years, the scale seen in the 2020s is thought to be unprecedented.¹⁰⁸ A lockdown covers almost all areas of life and restricts many different areas and organisations such as companies, schools, public services, or public offices (see *Restrictions of businesses / schools / public services / mass gatherings*).

Night curfews were also often imposed as a mild form of lockdown in countries such as the USA, France, the Netherlands, and Argentina. Night-time curfews were expected to reduce the number of meetings and decelerate the spread of the virus. However, public debate around night curfews is heated. They are considered strong government interference in civil rights with any positive impact on public health to be still proven. Initial studies suggest that night curfews are not an effective measure to limit virus transmission when various other intervention measures have already been imposed.¹⁰⁹

By whom and where can it be applied?

Lockdowns are compulsory political measures that can be useful if life-threatening pathogens are spread via aerosols in the air. Target groups are the general public; however, people in certain age groups or with certain health conditions can also be specifically addressed by this type of measure.

Impact

Although lockdowns are effective at reducing the spread of COVID-19, unintended side-effects include increases in mental health issues, bankruptcy of firms and losses of jobs and incomes. In an April 2020 report, UN Women warned that pandemic restrictions exacerbate gender inequalities, and have also led to an increase in domestic violence.¹¹⁰ Lockdowns impact all spheres of life: the economy, cultural activities and even the well-being of individuals. Vulnerable population groups are hit especially hard, e.g., care home residents who are not allowed to meet family and friends, or refugees who are the first to be excluded from a labour market under strain.

Municipality officials interviewed during the STEP_UP project stated that the positive outcome of lockdowns was the fact that the spread of the virus was stopped. On the other hand, they suggested that the value of a lockdown and its phases be more clearly communicated to avoid criticism. In addition, respondents stated that more checks, especially in rural areas, would be advisable to better enforce this measure.

Lockdowns in practice

Spain: On 14 March 2020, the National Government of Spain announced that the entire population of the country (around 47 million) had to be confined to curb the spread of COVID-19. Citizens could only leave their homes to buy groceries and pharmaceutical products, go to banks or hospitals, take care of dependent persons, or walk their dogs. Additionally, while on the street, they always had to be unaccompanied, and while they could go to work, most workplaces were closed to the public. As of 2 May 2020, fixed timetables regulated leaving one's home for non-essential physical exercise. People who needed special attention and people aged 70+ could go out between 7-8pm accompanied by one person. The outing had to take place within one km from home with a distance of 2 meters from other people. Adults and teenagers aged 14 and over could go out for physical activities once a day between 6am and 10am or between 8pm and 11pm. In villages with less than 5,000 inhabitants, the different timeframes didn't apply and people could go out under the same conditions between 6am and 11pm.¹¹¹

The Netherlands: On 15 March 2020, the Netherlands called on its population to go into lockdown and, if possible, not to leave their homes. Homes could only be left to go shopping or if work couldn't be done digitally. From 24 March onwards, measures were intensified and non-essential businesses such as casinos, gambling halls or campsites were closed unless they could guarantee permanent social distancing.¹¹² Starting on 31 March, there was further tightening of the rules, whereupon all public institutions such as museums, theatres, and sports associations were forced to close, putting the country into full lockdown.¹¹³

Political Measures

Restrictions of businesses / schools / public services / mass gatherings

Description

During lockdowns (see *Lockdown*), there are often closures of companies, schools or public institutions and services. In addition, these restrictions are usually linked to restrictions on gatherings. All these closures have the purpose of containing transmission of a virus.

Measures to **restrict or regulate businesses** usually differentiate between essential and non-essential businesses. Related measures have been developed, among others, for supermarkets, grocery stores, pharmacies, retail businesses, shopping centres, personal grooming businesses (like hair salons), construction, telecommunication and information services, mining and quarrying, warehousing, and support activities for transportation. Businesses that remain open usually have to apply preventive measures (see *Preventive measures*), such as a maximum number of clients, minimum distance between persons, offer sanitisers and ensure that masks are worn.

Schools that were **closed** or **regulated** included pre-schools or childcare facilities (up to 5 years old), primary schools (5-10 years old), and secondary schools (10–18 years old). Home schooling and alternating online with on-site teaching to smaller groups of pupils can, among other alternatives, complement learning. Purchasing equipment for air cleaning is recommended.

Regulated government functions may refer to issuing or processing documents, government meetings, including suspension of parliamentary work, working hours in public offices, or working from home offices. Public services subject to regulations are, among others, libraries, museums, galleries, parks, campsites, beaches, and waste management services.

Restrictions on mass gatherings can include cancelling or postponing annually recurring events or commercial events, or reducing prison population through early release.

By whom and where can it be applied?

Most containment measures are imposed by governments and designed to slow down and reduce the spread of diseases. Of course, business leaders or organisers are free to close their businesses or postpone events. The target group is the entire society, from working people to schoolchildren and students.

Impact

As a result of the above restrictions, contact in public and private spaces is prevented, reducing the spread of the virus. However, restrictions differ greatly in terms of their social consequences.

For example, some **government functions** can be easily transferred to digital procedures but, on the other hand, restriction of services means hardships for population groups who depend on them.

School restrictions impose high emotional burdens on children and youths because they are deprived of the company of others. They are also a burden for parents who have to homeschool their children while working from home. Closures and regulatory measures limit the spread of the virus but can be emotionally exhausting for children and youths as well as mentally and physically exhausting for parents.

Restrictions on businesses impact society because they can seriously upset their owners, and cause shortages of certain products and services for clients. Hence, political measures concerning relief to businesses often include financial assistance to business owners, employees, or self-employed workers in the targeted economic areas. The European Commission has invested in SURE loans that assist Member States in addressing sudden increases in public expenditure to preserve employment following the coronavirus pandemic.

Restrictions on mass gatherings can be useful in pandemics characterised by viruses that are spread via aerosols (not AIDS or Ebola), for which mass gatherings offer especially good conditions. Restrictions on mass gatherings mainly impact leisure activities.

Restriction measures in practice

Croatia: On 19 March 2020, the government of Croatia ordered the closure of libraries, museums and galleries to contain the spread of COVID-19. Moreover, the government obliged employers to organise work from home where possible and cancel meetings and trips to other countries. On 27 April, libraries, museums and galleries were allowed to reopen.

Germany: On 20 April 2020, the government of Lower Saxony (Germany) ordered pre-schools and childcare facilities to be provided for children whose parents worked in critical infrastructures. This included medical, health and public-sector workers, police, firefighters as well as workers in emergency relief services and the criminal system. This special measure also included children of people facing severe hardships, for instance threat of layoff and substantial loss of income.¹¹⁴

Description

Vaccination is a simple, safe and effective way to protect individuals and populations from infectious diseases before coming into contact with them. Vaccines help to activate the immune system by creating antibodies as if you were actually exposed to a disease. This way, if you are exposed in the future, chances are that symptoms will be mild or that there will be no symptom. Vaccines are made using several different processes. They may contain live viruses that have been attenuated (weakened or altered so as not to cause illness), inactivated or killed organisms or viruses, inactivated toxins (for bacterial diseases where toxins generated by the bacteria, and not the bacteria themselves, cause illness), or merely segments of the pathogens (this includes both sub-unit and conjugate vaccines).

There are vaccines for numerous diseases and today's routine immunisations have significantly reduced illnesses, deaths and spread of diseases globally. Some examples of diseases for which there is a vaccine are: diphtheria, influenza, hepatitis A, hepatitis B, Herpes zoster, HPV, measles, mumps, whooping cough, pneumococcal disease, polio, rotavirus, rubella, tetanus and chickenpox.

Vaccination is the administration of a substance to a person and, therefore, also involves some potential risks. These risks are, however, very small and far below the risks of contracting a disease. At least one of the vaccines for COVID-19 has been approved for the entire population over the age of 12 while the others are recommended for those above 18. Governments across the world are encouraging citizens to get vaccinated to help decrease the spread of the disease and the implications it has on people and healthcare systems.¹¹⁵ Even though the measure is a public health measure at its core, the decision to purchase and prescribe vaccines is a political one, which is the basis for its inclusion in the political measures (see *Financial resources / subsidies*).

By whom and where can it be applied?

Although vaccination is essentially a public health measure, in this report it is classified as a policy measure. This is because the decision to use vaccination is based on the political will to enforce it and purchase resources such as syringes. However, provided the right policies are in place and sufficient vaccine doses are available, vaccination is a social measure and everyone can contribute to disease control with just a few needlesticks.

Impact

So far studies have shown that vaccines that are authorised for use in most parts of the world are effective at protecting against symptomatic, lab-confirmed diseases. In large clinical trials/studies, where people were given the vaccines, all of the substances worked very well to prevent people from becoming sick with symptomatic, lab-confirmed COVID-19. Nevertheless, it is important to receive all recommended doses of the vaccines because they help to ensure longer-term protection. All the COVID-19 vaccines authorized for use in the European Union are highly effective at preventing severe outcomes including hospitalisations, ICU admission, severe diseases and deaths.

In terms of impact, vaccination programmes have clear direct costs at any point in time. These costs include purchasing the vaccine, health care personnel and infrastructure to maintain this chain (see *Financial resources / subsidies*). However, the reduction in morbidity and mortality associated with successful vaccine programmes, through a combination of direct and indirect protection, has led to reduced incidence of diseases and their associated treatments and healthcare costs.¹¹⁶

Municipality officials interviewed as part of the STEP_UP project stated that vaccination offers a way out of closures as a positive result. On the other hand, they stated that in future pandemics, better communication (see *Communication Measures*) is needed to increase vaccination rates. Other respondents even recommended mandatory vaccination, but this may be seen as jeopardising citizens' sense of autonomy and having negative effects on social satisfaction.

Vaccination measures in practice

Israel launched its COVID-19 vaccination campaign on 20 December 2020 but preparations for it began months before then. Over the course of 2020, Israel signed vaccine purchase contracts with several pharmaceutical companies at the forefront of COVID-19 vaccine development. In Israel people are notified that they are eligible to get vaccinated with an SMS. Alternatively, they can just walk into the premises of their healthcare providers and immediately see whether they are eligible or not. Israel had the fastest vaccine rollouts which contributed to numerous positive factors.¹¹⁷

Portugal: With 94.5% of the population having already received one dose, Portugal is one of the European countries with the most effective vaccination campaign.¹¹⁸ In order to build trust in vaccinations, the Portuguese Directorate General of Health recruited 5000 micro-influencers who were able to provide trusted information to communities. Thanks to this personal and social approach, this decision helped to dispel doubts early in the crisis and has also contributed to Portugal having one of the highest vaccination rates in Europe today.¹¹⁹

Conclusions and Perspectives

Being and staying prepared for pandemic emergencies is an important task at national policy level. The outbreak of COVID-19 found many European countries unprepared. In March 2020, when more experienced countries had already taken effective measures against the spread of the virus, European Health Ministers still shook hands in meetings, and the President of a public health institute stated that “the virus is not spreading very widely around the world”.¹²⁰ At that time, effective measures were thought to be a special characteristic of authoritarian regimes such as China, Singapore or Vietnam where mass testing to identify and separate infected persons or electronic tracing was applied. However, other countries such as New Zealand and Australia also implemented effective measures with locally restricted lockdowns and drastic penalties in case of breaches. Even if these examples were the consequence of certain framework conditions (i.e., low population density, isolation on an island or previous pandemics), it is still important to understand how to learn from them. Moreover, it should be self-evident not to condemn other solutions in the media.

Preparedness is the key

In this context, being better prepared for disease outbreaks should be a goal for the future. Among others, the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) provides information and practical tools for pandemic preparedness planning and aims at a cross-sectoral approach over longer periods of time and a continuous process based on several key elements:

- Pandemic preparedness, response and evaluation should be built on generic preparedness platforms, structures, mechanisms and plans for crisis and emergency management.
- As far as possible, pandemic preparedness should aim to strengthen existing systems rather than developing new ones, in particular components of national seasonal influenza prevention and control programmes.
- Adequate resources must be allocated for all aspects of pandemic preparedness and response.
- Pandemic response requires that business continuity and surge capacity plans be developed for the health sector and all other sectors that could be affected by a pandemic in order to ensure sustained capacity during a pandemic.
- The response to a pandemic must be evidence-based where this is available and commensurate with the threat. Planning should be based on pandemics of differing severity while the response needs to be based on the actual circumstances as determined by national and global risk assessments.
- Not all countries will be able to contribute to global risk assessment, nor conduct evaluations such as pandemic vaccine effectiveness. They must all have the capacity to access and interpret data for risk assessment provided by the WHO, ECDC, and other countries or sources.
- In the future, a lot of responsibility will therefore lie on countries with greater financial resources to assist in terms of information and health resources such as masks or vaccines. Supporting other governments and finding a more international approach to such global problems should be a priority in any future pandemics.¹²¹

The above-mentioned key elements can also be seen in the graph on the next page. To facilitate the work on pandemic preparedness, the ECDC also provides helpful information and guidelines, such as *a list of national pandemic preparedness plans*, *a guide for the revision of national preparedness plans*, *an assessment tool for influenza pandemic preparedness plans*, and national examples for *business continuity planning*.

*Key elements of the pandemic preparedness planning circle.
Source: [European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control](#)*

Limitations

Overall, regardless of the specific context, it is highly important that every country assess its approaches, evaluate their impacts, and is prepared for future pandemics that are highly likely to occur. This Manual is intended to contribute to an early understanding of possible practices to contain communicable diseases in the future and, if appropriate, implement them more quickly, more effectively and in a more targeted manner. It should be added that the Manual by no means presents all the measures used in reality, as this would simply exceed its scope. Nevertheless, this information can help different target groups to explore and understand possible guidelines and practices. It should also be noted that the measures and guidelines hereby discussed serve as recommendations which cannot often be seen as clearly positive or negative. Therefore, the measures that have been suggested must always be considered in terms of prevention and range of effects they might have on society. Fittingly, it is important to note that there is no all-purpose weapon against pandemics and that in many cases there is a trade-off between containment policy and societal satisfaction and sense of civil freedom.

Project Outcomes

The STEP_UP thematical reports

The STEP_UP thematical reports highlighted various topics related to virus containment and measures that can be taken. The contents of the thematical reports were one of the main sources for this Manual. The thematical reports can be opened by clicking on the various areas. Topics were distributed as follows:

- **WISE** from Spain compiled **communication measures**.
- **SHINE** from Portugal dealt with a **wide range of social prevention measures**.
- **ISIS** from Germany summarised **political measures**.
- **CIPH** from Croatia brought together **health and social care measures**.
- **AFEdemy** from the Netherlands dealt with measures for **early detection of communicable diseases**.

The virtual library of confinement measures

At the beginning of the project, all participating partners collected measures, approaches to solutions or practical examples of policy implementation in the thematic area of their national reports. This work resulted in a database with more than 200 entries, which can be found on the website under the **STEP_UP library**. Possible policy implementations and practices can be filtered by country, domain and potential outcomes, thus providing an interesting tool for decision-makers to come up with ideas and find possible solutions from practice.

STEP_UP survey asking for target groups' opinions on Corona measures

The aim of the STEP_UP survey was to learn more about the perspectives and professional experiences of people working on the COVID-19 outbreak. Pandemic measures collected during desk research and the national reports have been evaluated directly by users and affected parties in order to identify shortcomings and possible improvements. In total, recommendations and criticisms were collected on 18 different measures against the virus and 133 people answered the survey which can be accessed by clicking this [link](#).

The STEP_UP online game

The core of STEP_UP is an educational game that can also be used as a recreational game by the general public. In STEP_UP, players aim to stop a pandemic from spreading. A list of pandemic events is experienced, and players have the opportunity to implement measures in order to be able to choose those that would help preventing the virus from spreading without damaging the economy or causing societal anger. The game is also intended to help people better understand and follow government measures (which in reality they do not always do) and distinguish between true facts and myths and fake news. The game is available from February 2023 and can be accessed via the **STEP_UP website** or this [Link](#).

The STEP_UP training toolkit

Moreover, a supportive and innovative training toolkit will be released on the website that includes the game, training materials and guidance that can also be used in workshops. The Game and workshop toolkit will enable learners to build on existing competences and increase resilience to help their communities in crisis situations.

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